

Platinum(II) and Platinum(IV) Bigunides

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Several robust complexes of platinum(II) and platinum(IV) with biguanide ($C_2N_5H_7=BigH$) having the composition $[Pt(BigH_2)]X_2$ and *trans* $[Pt(OH)_2(BigH)_2]X_2$ have been synthesised by the interaction of chlorides of platinum(II) and (IV) with alkaline biguanide. Fusion of chloroplatinic acid with biguanide normal sulphate produced *tris* (biguanidinium)platinum(IV) sulphate from which the *cis*-dihydroxobis (biguanidinium)platinum(IV) hydroxide was isolated by treatment with concentrated alkali. The *cis* and *trans* varieties of $[Pt(OH)_2(BigH)_2](OH)_2$ were characterised by the isolation of $[Pt(BigH)_2](OH)_2$ from the *cis* variety of the compound.

PLATINUM(II) and (IV) show a great preference for attachment to nitrogen, halogen, cyanides, phosphorous, arsenic and sulphur. All kinds of cationic and anionic complexes with coordination numbers four and six for platinum(II) and platinum(IV) respectively are formed as also the chelates with β -diketones, dialkylglyoximes, salicylaloximes etc. Some of these compounds viz. trimethylplatinum β -diketones are known to take up unusual structures in order to satisfy hexa-coordination.^{1,2} The robust nature of the complexes with phosphorous and arsenic ligands is mainly due to the formation of strong metal-ligand π -bonding. In case of donor atoms without favourable d orbitals, linking occurs through π -bonding from the overlap of filled $d\pi$ -orbitals with empty $p\pi$ -antibonding molecular orbitals of these ligands. Considering the structure of biguanide molecule with delocalised π -electron system,³ it was thought interesting to study the complex forming capacity of the ligand with respect to platinum(II) and platinum(IV). This has led to the preparation of a number of very stable platinum biguanide complexes.⁴

Platinum(II) has been found to give four covalent biguanide complexes of general formula $[Pt(BigH_2)]X_2$ where X=halide ion, OH, NO_3 or $\frac{1}{2}SO_4$. The conductivity measurement of the chloride indicates that the compound is bi-univalent electrolyte.

Chloroplatinic acid or potassium chloroplatinate on boiling with alkaline biguanide produces a dirty white crystalline precipitate of composition $[Pt(OH)_2(BigH)_2](OH).2H_2O$. A series of salts, namely chloride, bromide, nitrate, perchlorate, sulphate etc.

was prepared from this compound. *Tris*(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) complex, could not, however, be obtained by this method.

Fusion of chloroplatinic acid with biguanide normal sulphate at a temperature of $160^\circ-165^\circ C$ produced a yellow insoluble mass, which, when digested with water and washed thoroughly to free it from unreacted biguanide, gave a compound of composition $[Pt(BigH)_3](SO_4)_2.2H_2O$. Treatment of this compound with ammonium hydroxide produced the basic salt $[Pt(BigH)_3(OH)_2]SO_4.4H_2O$ and a similar treatment with concentrated alkali resulted in the formation of a yellow di-hydroxo-bis (biguanidinium)-platinum(IV) hydroxide. This, however, differed in crystalline shape and colour from the grey $[Pt(OH)_2(BigH)_2](OH)_2$, prepared by the interaction of potassium chloroplatinate, biguanide sulphate and alkali. The sulphate of the yellow compound was prepared by the addition of excess sulphate ion to the mother liquor after the separation of *tris*(biguanidinium) platinum(IV) sulphate. The corresponding chloride and perchlorate have also been prepared.

Considering the methods of preparation, the needle-shaped grey di-hydroxo-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) hydroxide may be considered as the *trans* form and the yellow compound of the same composition as the *cis* variety. This has also been substantiated by the preparation of ethylene-diamino-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) sulphate from the yellow compound. The grey variety, on the other hand, failed to react in a similar manner with ethylenediamine. All these platinum(IV) complexes are quite stable to acids and alkalis.

Tetracoordinated platinum(II) and hexacoordinated platinum(IV) biguanides can be represented as in Figs. I, II.

Fig I

Fig II

Experimental

Bis(biguanidinium)platinum(II) chloride :

The compound was prepared by digesting platinum(II) chloride (1g) with biguanide base (2g) in 20 ml water on a hot plate at a temperature of the boiling point of the solution. Platinum(II) chloride reacted slowly to give at first a green product which gradually changed to a wine-red solution. The filtrate was concentrated on a water bath and cooled, when white crystals of bis(biguanidinium)platinum(II) chloride separated out. This was filtered, washed with small amount of cold water and finally dried in air.

The compound forms well defined plates which are soluble in water. The compound is stable in acid and gives the precipitate of corresponding hydroxide on treatment with alkali.

Bis(biguanidinium)platinum(II)hydroxide :

An aqueous solution of bis (biguanidinium) platinum(II) chloride was treated with caustic soda

solution with constant stirring. Silver-white flakes of bis (biguanidinium) platinum(II) hydroxide separated out, which were filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dried over caustic potash.

The substance reacts strongly alkaline to litmus. It can liberate ammonia from ammonium salts. When heated to 110°C, it loses water forming the anhydro-base Pt(Big)₂.

Bis(biguanidinium)platinum(II)sulphate :

It was obtained as a white crystalline precipitate by the addition of a concentrated solution of sodium sulphate to that of bis (biguanidinium) platinum(II) chloride. The crystals were filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

The substance when recrystallised from boiling water, forms glistening, white, wooly, needle-shaped crystals. It can also be prepared by treating the base with dilute sulphuric acid.

Tris(biguanidinium)platinum(IV)sulphate :

Potassium hexachloroplatinate(IV) hexahydrate was taken in an agate mortar and mixed thoroughly with biguanide normal sulphate. The mixture was then gradually heated to about 160—165°C on a sand bath. The mass first softened and then melted and it was kept in the molten condition for about half an hour. It was then cooled and digested with water. The yellow residue was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dried in air.

The substance is not acted upon by acids; but alkali changes it to the bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) hydroxide. With dilute ammonium hydroxide it gives the corresponding hydroxo sulphate.

Tris(biguanidinium) platinum (IV) hydroxo sulphate :

Tris (biguanidinium) platinum(IV) sulphate was digested with dilute (2N) ammonium hydroxide in the cold when the yellow colour of the compound faded to light cream. This was filtered, washed with water and dried in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride and caustic potash. On dehydration at 110°C the substance loses 6 molecules of water and may be represented by the formula [Pt(Big)₃(BigH)]SO₄.

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Tris (biguanidinium) platinum(IV) chloride :

Chloroplatinic acid hexahydrate was mixed thoroughly with biguanide normal chloride in an agate mortar. The mixture was then heated slowly on a sand bath when the mass softened at about 80–90°C and then solidified again on losing water. It finally melted at 160°C and was kept in this condition for half-an-hour. The cold product was digested with water and the orange residue was filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

The chloride is sparingly soluble in water. On treatment with alkali it gave the corresponding hydroxide.

Tris (biguanidinium)platinum(IV) perchlorate :

Tris(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) chloride was boiled with perchloric acid (60 per cent) and the solution filtered hot through a sintered glass funnel. The filtrate was left in the cold when diamond shaped glistering yellow crystals of the perchlorate separated out.

ANALYSIS OF COMPLEXES (%)

Substance		Pt	N	C	H	Anions (Cl/SO ₄ /ClO ₄)	H ₂ O
[Pt(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Found	38.24	27.85	—	—	14.18	7.21
	Required	38.71	27.76			14.08	7.16
[Pt(BigH) ₃](OH) ₂	Found	45.18	32.32	11.96	3.88	—	8.82
	Required	45.26	32.46	11.13	3.71		8.35
[Pt(BigH) ₃]SO ₄ ·1.5H ₂ O	Found	37.92	27.08	—	—	18.38	5.84
	Required	37.50	26.92			18.49	5.20
[Pt(BigH) ₃](SO ₄) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Found	27.02	28.80	9.83	3.21	26.21	4.58
	Required	26.86	28.93	9.92	3.44	26.45	4.96
[Pt(BigH) ₃](OH) ₂ SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Found	28.02	30.14	—	—	13.53	14.92
	Required	27.85	30.00			13.71	15.49
[Pt(BigH) ₃]Cl ₄	Found	30.82	32.51	—	—	22.31	—
	Required	30.46	32.81			22.19	
[Pt(BigH) ₃](ClO ₄) ₄ ·3H ₂ O	Found	20.51	21.93	7.56	2.66	41.53	—
	Required	20.53	22.10	7.58	2.84	41.90	
<i>Cis</i> [Pt(OH) ₂ (BigH) ₂](OH) ₂	Found	42.43	29.83	10.44	4.00	—	7.82
	Required	41.93	30.10	10.32	3.87		7.79
<i>Cis</i> [Pt(OH) ₂ (BigH) ₂]SO ₄	Found	37.12	26.37	—	—	18.10	—
	Required	37.00	26.57			18.22	
[Pt _{en} (BigH) ₂](OH) ₂ SO ₄	Found	33.52	28.34	12.17	3.89	16.42	5.98
	Required	33.23	28.62	12.27	4.09	16.36	6.53
<i>trans</i> [Pt(OH) ₂ (BigH) ₂](OH) ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Found	37.23	26.82	9.58	3.95	—	16.82
	Required	37.57	26.97	9.25	4.62		17.34
<i>trans</i> [Pt(OH) ₂ (BigH) ₂]Cl ₂	Found	39.02	27.82	—	—	14.23	—
	Required	38.84	27.89			14.15	
<i>trans</i> [Pt(OH) ₂ (BigH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Found	35.82	30.38	8.42	2.94	—	—
	Required	35.13	30.27	8.65	2.88		
<i>trans</i> [Pt(OH) ₂ (BigH) ₂]SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Found	34.72	24.82	—	—	17.25	6.42
	Required	34.63	24.86			17.05	6.39

Cis-di-hydroxo-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) hydroxide :

Tris (biguanidinium) platinum(IV) sulphate was digested with alkali over a low flame when it slowly dissolved. Glistening yellow crystals separated out on cooling the filtrate. The crystals were filtered, washed thoroughly with water and then dried in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride and caustic potash. The yield is very poor.

Unlike the tris(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) hydroxide, this compound is soluble in hot water and alkali. It reacts alkaline to litmus. At 120°C it loses two molecules of water to form $Pt(OH)_2(Big)_2$. There was no further loss in weight even at 350°C.

Cis-dihydroxo-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) sulphate:

The compound was prepared by adding dilute (2N) sulphuric acid to the yellow di-hydroxo-bis (biguanidinium) platinum(IV) hydroxide. The same compound can also be obtained by the addition of a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate to the mother liquor remaining after the separation of tris (biguanidinium) platinum(IV) sulphate, when yellow crystals separated out on standing for a few days.

Ethylenediamino-bis (biguanidinium)platinum(IV) hydroxide sulphate :

Di-hydroxo-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) sulphate was boiled with an aqueous solution of ethylenediamine hydrate. A canary yellow precipitate was formed. This was filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

The compound is completely insoluble in water. At 120°C it changes to $[Pt(en)(Big)_2]SO_4$ by losing two molecules of water.

Trans-di-hydroxo-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) hydroxide :

Potassium chloroplatinate was boiled with alkaline biguanide solution for about half-an-hour.

This was filtered hot and left over-night. Glistening grey needle shaped crystals separated out from the orange solution which were filtered, washed with water and dried over fused calcium chloride and caustic potash.

The compound is soluble in alkali. The solution on neutralisation with acids produces the corresponding salts. The compound reacts alkaline to litmus. At 130°C it loses five molecules of water per mole of the substance.

Trans-di-hydroxo-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) chloride :

A solution of *trans*-dihydroxo-bis(biguanidinium) platinum(IV) hydroxide in dilute hydrochloric acid was evaporated on a water bath to a small volume. On cooling, dirty white crystals separated out which were washed with water and dried as usual.

Trans-dihydroxo-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) nitrate:

The white sparingly soluble crystalline compound was formed by the interaction of the corresponding base with nitric acid (6N). The compound hydrolyses slowly giving basic salt.

Trans-dihydroxo-bis(biguanidinium)platinum(IV) sulphate :

This was prepared from an aqueous solution of the corresponding chloride and a saturated solution sulphate. The fine white needle-shaped crystals, that separated, were recrystallised from boiling water, filtered, washed and dried as usual.

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Chromatographic Studies on Metal Complexes Part I Paper Chromatography of Square planar bis(biguanide) Complexes of Copper (II), Nickel (II) and Palladium (II)

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A paper chromatographic study of square planar bis(biguanide) complexes of copper(II), nickel(II) and palladium(II) in aqueous pyridine developer has been made. R_f values decrease in the order: Ni(II) > Cu(II) > Pd(II). R_f values increase with increasing alkyl substitution in the biguanide moiety of a particular metal complex. Phenyl substitution lowers the R_f . Substantial amount of pyridine in the developer results in two spots with bis(biguanide) copper(II). The following equilibrium is suggested:

MOST studies on paper chromatography of inorganic cations have been directed with a view to their identification via characteristic R_f value in a chosen developer. Paper chromatographic studies on metal complexes have mainly veered around inert cobalt (III)¹. Little work on the complexes of other transition metals has appeared in the literature. The purpose of this study of square planar bis(biguanide) metal(II) complexes has been multifold: (1) to determine a suitable developer such that the complexes are chromatographed as genuine bis(biguanide) complexes; (2) to study the effect, if any, of substitution in the biguanide moiety on the R_f values of the complexes and (3) to determine the influence of the transition metals on R_f .

Methods and Materials:

The complexes have been obtained by following published procedures². Their purity was checked by analysis and spectral measurement.

Experimental Conditions:

For the purpose of putting spots most of the complexes were dissolved in water at room temperature or in warm water. In a few cases (e.g. those of copper dimethyl, diethyl and phenylbiguanide) complexes were dissolved in ethanol because of greater solubility in this solvent. The following developers were selected after a number of trials:

Developer I: 100ml of 0.5M aqueous KCl + 5ml pyridine

Developer II: 100ml of 1.0M aqueous KCl + 5ml pyridine

Developer III: 70ml of 0.5M aqueous KCl
30ml 1 : 1 pyridine

The total volume of the developer was about 100ml. The chromatographic chamber was saturated with the vapour of the developer for at least one day. Chromatography was carried out on Whatman No. 1 paper strips (3cm × 52 cm) using ascending technique. The sample solution was applied at a point 8cm from the end and the developer was allowed to travel 28-30cm from the point of application of the spot. The time required was about 3 hours.

For the detection of copper and nickel complexes rubeanic acid in ethanol was satisfactory. Palladium complexes were detected with acidified (HCl) solution of rubeanic acid. Bis(biguanide)copper(II) complex on spraying with rubeanic acid gave an oval shaped spot, the lower portion of the spot having a dominant brown colour while the upper part had the usual dirty green colour of copper rubeanate. But most of the substituted biguanide copper(II) complexes gave only a dirty green coloured spot on spraying with rubeanic acid. Nickel complexes had the blue to blue violet colour of nickel rubeanate and palladium complexes a yellow colour of palladium rubeanate. The brown shade in the spot of bis(biguanide)copper(II) chloride was not subjected to any further investigation. R_f values were measured with respect to the centre of the distance between the front and the end of the spot. These R_f values were reproducible to within $\pm 0.02 R_f$ units.

Results and Discussion :

Developer I was quite satisfactory for identification and separation of copper(II) and palladium(II) bis(biguanide) complexes from one another. This developer was also suitable for separation and identification of bis(biguanide)copper(II) from bis (substituted biguanide)copper(II). In this developer both copper(II) and palladium(II) complexes provide well defined spots, those of copper(II) being ~ 2.5 — 3.0 cm in length and those of palladium(II) ~ 1.0 cm. Bis(phenylbiguanide)palladium(II)chloride alone gives large tailing (~ 5 cm). Unfortunately this developer provided a big sized (10-12cm) spot for bis (biguanide)nickel(II) complexes and was therefore not considered a suitable choice for these nickel (II) complexes. Suitable sized spots (~ 3 cm) of bis(biguanide)nickel(II) and bis(substituted biguanide)nickel(II) complexes were obtained using developer II which also allowed distinction between nickel(II) complexes themselves. But neither developer I nor developer II was found suitable for distinguishing bis(biguanide)palladium(II) and bis(substituted biguanide)palladium(II) complexes from one another. To achieve this distinction developer (III) was found suitable.

Yoneda¹ from a study of cobalt (III) complexes concluded that the cationic complexes are held strongly on the negatively charged cellulose anion of the filter paper. Thus in pure water as developer positively charged complexes either did not travel at all or if they travelled they diffused considerably along the filter paper. With distilled water alone most of our complexes either did not travel at all or diffused to a long distance (Fig. 1). Remembering that metal biguanide complexes are stable to dis-

Fig. 1. Chromatograms in 100 ml distilled water as developer

- (1) $[\text{Ni}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$;
- (2) $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$;
- (3) $[\text{Pd}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

sociation only at $\text{pH} \sim 7.0$, we tried several aqueous electrolytes as developers so that the cations of the electrolyte may quench the undesirable effect of the cellulose anion. Satisfactory spots were obtained with two sets of developers :

- A 0.5M (or 1M) aqueous ammonium acetate
- B. 0.5M (or 1M) aqueous KCl containing pyridine.

The first of these developers (A), although gave a $\text{PH} \sim 6.5$ to 6.8 where metal biguanides do not dissociate appreciably, were abandoned since spectrophotometric studies revealed that for all three copper(II) nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes there were substantial modification of the electronic spectra. These developers therefore do not give R_f values of the genuine complexes. The developers of category (B) provided the same electronic spectra of the complexes as is obtained in aqueous solution alone. Thus in 100 ml 0.5 M (or 1M) KCl containing 5ml pyridine we have the genuine chromatograms of our complexes.

Effect of KCl/pyridine : Variation of KCl concentration in aqueous pyridine reveals that R_f values of all complexes increase with increasing KCl concentration (Table 1). It is to be noted that neither KCl nor pyridine alone can give good spots (Fig. 2

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES OF $[\text{M}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ ($\text{M}=\text{Cu}(\text{II}), \text{Ni}(\text{II}), \text{Pd}(\text{II})$) WITH DIFFERENT DEVELOPERS

Complex	Developer I	Developer II
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	0.64	0.78
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	0.46	0.53
$[\text{Pd}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	0.10	0.23

Fig. 2 Chromatograms in 100ml 1M aqueous KCl as developer (1), (2) and (3) are as in Fig. 1.

and 3) but a suitable combination does (Fig. 4). Pyridine substantially increases the solubility of the complexes.

Fig. 3. Chromatograms in 100ml 5% pyridine in water as developer (1), (2) and (3) are as in Fig. 1.

Fig. 4. Chromatograms in 100ml 1M aqueous KCl+5ml pyridine as developer. (1), (2) and (3) are as in Fig. 1.

Fig. 5. Chromatograms in 70ml 0.5M aqueous KCl+30ml 1:1 pyridine. (1) $[Cu(BigH)_2]Cl_2$ (2) $CuCl_2$ (3) $[Cu(MeBigH)_2]Cl_2$ (4) $[Cu(EtBigH)_2]Cl_2$

Interestingly on raising the pyridine concentration and lowering the KCl concentration (developer III) bis(biguanide)copper(II) complex betrayed two distinct spots (Fig. 5), the one with higher R_f was less intense than the other with lower R_f . Furthermore the spot with higher R_f coincided with the spot of copper(II) chloride in the same developer and that with lower R_f had the characteristic shape of bis(biguanide) copper(II) in the same developer. An

explanation possibly lies in the assumption of the following equilibrium :

The low intensity of the tetrapyridinocopper(II) spot would point to the fact that the equilibrium is still favoured towards bis(biguanide)copper(II). With bis(alkylsubstitutedbiguanide)copper(II) distinct separation into two spots could not be achieved possibly because of the higher R_f values of the bis(alkylsubstituted biguanide) compared to that of the bis(biguanide)copper(II). This would lead to a smaller gap between the spots of tetrapyridine copper(II) and bis(alkylsubstituted biguanide) copper(II). But with developer III, nickel(II) complexes did not betray two distinct spots, although the size of the spot was substantially large (~ 9 cm). Bis(biguanide) palladium(II), however, exhibited only one sharp spot which is an evidence towards preponderance of only one species.

Effect of size of the complexes on R_f values : The increasing R_f values : $Pd < Cu < Ni$ corresponds to the decreasing size and weight of the complexes $Pd > Cu > Ni$ (Table 1 and Fig. 4).

Effect of substitution in biguanide moiety on R_f values :

On increasing alkyl substitution on N^1 atom of biguanide the R_f values of the corresponding copper(II), nickel(II) and palladium(II) bis (biguanide) complexes also increase. But phenyl substitution lowers the R_f (Table 2). Since biguanide and alkyl

TABLE 2— R_f VALUES OF $[M(BigH)_2]Cl_2$ and $[M(SUBSTITUTED BigH)_2]Cl_2$ WITH DIFFERENT DEVELOPERS

Complex	Developer II	Developer I	Developer III
	M=Ni(II)	M=Cu(II)	M=Pd(II)
$[M(BigH)_2]Cl_2$	0.78	0.46	0.40
$[M(Me BigH)_2]Cl_2$	0.83	0.52	0.51
$[M(Et BigH)_2]Cl_2$	0.86	0.64	0.58
$[M(Pr BigH)_2]Cl_2$	0.88	0.68	—
$[M(Me_2 BigH)_2]Cl_2$	0.90	0.72	—
$[M(Et_2 BigH)_2]Cl_2$	0.92	0.78	—
$[M(Ph BigH)_2]Cl_2$	0.76	0.44	0.33

BigH=biguanide ; MeBigH=methyl biguanide ; Et BigH=ethyl biguanide ; Pr¹ BigH=isopropyl biguanide ; Me₂BigH=dimethyl biguanide ; Et₂BigH=diethyl biguanide ; Ph BigH=phenylbiguanide.

biguanide have more or less similar basic character it is a reasonable guess that the attractive influence of the bipoisitive cations on the cellulose anion will be quite close. However, substitution of the hydrogen atom attached to the N¹ atom of the biguanide by hydrophobic groups would considerably reduce the chances of forming hydrogen bonded species with cellulose anions. This is expected to lead to a higher R_f with increasing substitution. Had solubility alone been responsible for differences in R_f values we would have observed a reverse order with increasing alkyl substitution. Increase of R_f values from biguanide to methyl biguanide and then to other alkyl biguanide is also likely to be connected with inductive influence of the electron releasing alkyl groups whereby the overall charge on the com-

plex cation may be diminished to some extent. This lowering of charge will enhance the R_f values. On the contrary electron withdrawing phenyl substitution will lead to a lower R_f.

This is a pleasure to acknowledge our indebtedness to the C.S.I.R. for financial assistance to one of us (R.K.R.). We thank Dr. S. Ghosh Majumdar and Dr. S. Thakur for their kind advice and suggestions during the course of the work.

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